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UNSTEADY NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS OF SUBSONIC AND TRANSONIC FLOWS IN A CENTRIFUGAL COMPRESSOR STAGE WITH A VANED DIFFUSER

Luying Zhang, William T. Cousins, Guoping Xia,
Om Sharma
United Technologies Research Center
East Hartford, Connecticut, USA

Vishnu Sishtla
UTC Climate, Controls & Security
Syracuse, New York, USA

ABSTRACT

Unsteady numerical simulations have been carried out for a centrifugal compressor stage with a vane diffuser. The results are compared to the ones from steady simulations at both high rotational speed (transonic flow) and low rotational speed (subsonic flow). The results show that for the transonic flow the interaction between the shockwave and blade wake passing causes strong unsteadiness. The pressure rise and efficiency is overestimated by the steady simulation and the flow non-uniformity along the annulus in the diffuser domain cannot be captured. For the subsonic flow, the stall side flow separates at the inducer shroud first, which causes the performance to drop significantly. Flow in the diffuser domain remains periodic. The steady simulation also overestimates the stage performance, but the prediction agrees much better with the unsteady simulation. Frequency analysis has been carried out to better understand the unsteady blade row interaction. It shows that in the transonic case, the diffuser domain separating flow pattern is not stationary, it rotates along the annulus and generates pressure fluctuations at additional frequencies; while in the subsonic case the pressure fluctuations are mainly at the blade passing frequencies.

INTRODUCTION

Centrifugal compressors have widespread industrial applications such as refrigeration, pipeline compression and automotive industry [1]. The operating limits of a centrifugal compressor are defined by the maximum and minimum rotating speed, the choke region for high flow conditions and the stall limit for low flow conditions. For a variable speed machine a well-predicted performance map is important, because quite often the compressor has to function at off-design conditions and the system operating/control logic needs to be developed based on the compressor performance.

The numerical simulation of the near stall behaviour in a centrifugal machine has been a challenge just as it has been for axial machine. In addition, the path into instability in centrifugal compressors is less studied compared to axial machines. Previous research work have been carried out for automotive turbochargers as the compressors often operate near the stability limit or in close proximity to the surge line [2]. Both spike and modal stall inception have been observed in experiments on a centrifugal compressor with a vane diffuser. The path into compression system instability is altered by the bleed air near the impeller exit. The vaneless and semi-vaneless space between the impeller and diffuser has been identified as the key region to determine the stability limit. Unsteady numerical simulations have been carried out on a low speed centrifugal compressor and the results were compared to measurements [3]. The evolution of the tornado-type vortex and leading edge vortex is thought to be the trigger of the diffuser stall. The unsteady flow in the vane diffuser of a transonic high-pressure-ratio centrifugal compressor has been analysed in detail from CFD results [4]. The interaction between the diffuser vane bow shock wave and the impeller blade is investigated, however only at stable operation condition.

In a chiller compression system with refrigerants as working fluid, the centrifugal compressor also frequently functions at various rotational speeds and at different mass flow rate conditions. A large operational range is desirable apart from achieving the required pressure ratio with good efficiency. During the variable speed operation both subsonic and transonic flow can exist in the compressor stage. The stall mechanism is more complex and can happen at different regions of a stage [5]. The mechanism to trigger flow instability should be studied in detail. The understanding will help in both the design phase and the system control. Flow in a centrifugal compressor stage is inherently unsteady and previous study [6] shows that the steady simulations may give very different predictions

compared to unsteady simulations. Therefore both steady and unsteady numerical simulations are carried out in the current work.

A high speed centrifugal compressor (pressure ratio around 5.0) with a vane diffuser has been studied through numerical simulations. The low solidity vane diffuser was originally designed to improve the efficiency of the stage with a sacrifice of operational range. The flow unsteadiness in the stage has been studied in detail. The goal is to gain more knowledge on the flow field at different rotating speeds with a focus on understanding the limiting factor for achieving a larger operation range. It also aims at evaluating the accuracy of the numerical methods by comparing the steady simulation results to the unsteady simulation results.

For this compressor, at the designed rotational speed the flow exiting the impeller passage is supersonic and a shockwave is formed at the diffuser vane leading edge. When the rotational speed is reduced to 75% of the designed value, the stage flow becomes mostly subsonic. The unsteady blade row interaction between impeller and diffuser in both these scenarios is analyzed in detail.

METHODOLOGIES

UTCFD, an unsteady Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (URANS) solver was used for all the computations in this work. The in-house code (structured) was first presented in [7] and has been validated on different cases. It has second-order-accuracy (both in space and time) and uses explicit-in-time numerical method with a multi-grid acceleration technique. The solver is density based for compressible flow equations. Both ideal gas and real gas can be solved as the working fluid. For the current simulation, the refrigerant fluid (R1233zd) property is taken from REFPROP v9.1. It is simulated by the solver as real gas using a look-up gas table rather than with ideal gas assumptions. All simulations use the $k-\omega$ turbulence model without wall functions. For unsteady full-wheel simulations the sliding interface is used to connect the rotating and stationary domain. For steady simulations single passage domain is used and the mixing-plane model is adopted at all interfaces. For unsteady simulations, 70 time steps are used for each impeller pitch (770 time steps for a whole revolution). Total pressure, total temperature and flow angles are specified at the inlet boundary and the static pressure is specified at the outlet boundary.

Figure 1 shows the layout of the computational domain which consists of the inlet guide vane (7 blades), impeller (11 blades with 11 splitters) and vane diffuser (7 blades). Towards the exit of the domain a bend to axial direction and a converging nozzle is added to have better control on the numerical stability [8]. Previous numerical studies show that this configuration makes the computational domain less stiff and stabilizes (numerically) the simulation towards the stall side. For high speed simulation the rotational speed is 12420 RPM and for low speed simulation it is 9315 RPM.

Figure 1 Computational domain layout

The mesh for all calculations was generated using Numeca's *autogrid*TM. An O-4H block topology was employed around the blade and the tip mesh uses an O-H topology. There are 89 nodes in the spanwise direction (17 cells in the tip clearance) with the maximum Y_{plus} around 5.5. The total number of mesh points is around 12.2 million. Figure 2 shows the mesh detail at IGV/impeller interface and impeller/diffuser interface.

Figure 2 Mesh detail of the computational domain

MAIN RESULTS

In the first part of the discussion, the performance prediction of the centrifugal compressor stage from steady simulations is compared to the previous datum case. The factors that limit the operational range are discussed. Then the results from the unsteady simulations are compared to the ones from the steady simulations. The difference between the two is examined in detail. A frequency analysis has been carried out to better understand the impeller/diffuser blade row interaction. This part is referred to as the 'transonic flow' simulations in the work.

In the second part, the 75% rotational speed results are reviewed. Again, both unsteady and steady simulations are carried out and the differences in performance prediction are discussed. The results are also compared to the ones from simulations at the design speed; therefore the influence of changing the rotational speed can be seen. Since the stage flow is mainly subsonic at 75% speed it is denoted as 'subsonic flow' in the following discussion.

Transonic Flow:

Figure 3 shows the total-to-total pressure ratio and the normalized total-to-total polytropic efficiency of the impeller and the stage (impeller + diffuser). The inlet station is downstream of the IGV row so the IGV loss is not included in the impeller/stage performance analysis. The performance of the same impeller with a 'vaneless' diffuser was referred to as the 'datum' case. They are also from steady simulations and are marked by the black lines

in Figure 3. It can be observed that the impeller T-T pressure ratio and the efficiency (blue lines with solid squares) agree well with the datum case. The stage performance (blue lines with hollow squares) shows that the vane diffuser has a better efficiency than the datum case, as expected. However the range is shortened in both the stall side and the choke side.

Figure 3 Total-to-total performances from both steady and unsteady simulations

The flow field at the last stable points towards both sides is shown in Figure 4. At high speed conditions (Figure 4), the Mach number exiting the impeller passage is above 1.0 and a shockwave can be observed in the diffuser passage. It can be seen that towards the choke side (Figure 4, right) there is a pressure side flow separation in the diffuser passage at both 10% span and 90% span positions. This separation is due to the flow incidence at such conditions and it triggers numerical oscillations for steady simulations. On the other side, when the flow rate is reduced the shock wave is moving upstream in the diffuser passage. There is a shock-induced separation on the suction side of the diffuser vane (Figure 4, a, left). This separation is triggered in the hub region (as can be seen on the 10% span plot) but not visible at 90% span. Numerical oscillation is also observed if the flow rate is further reduced. This suggests that towards the stall side the diffuser hub flow is the least stable in this design.

a) Mach number contour at 10% span (left: towards stall, right: towards choke)

b) Mach number contour at 90% span (left: towards stall, right: towards choke)

Figure 4 Mach number contour plots from steady simulations

The unsteady simulations have also been carried out for these conditions. The speed line performance is plotted in Figure 3 (red lines). The comparison between steady and unsteady results shows that the pressure rise predicted by the unsteady simulations is lower than that from the steady simulations at most conditions. In addition, both the impeller and stage efficiency is lower when the unsteadiness in the flow is considered. In particular, the steady simulations predict a 'stage efficiency' rise as the flow rate is reduced while the unsteady simulations show the efficiency is dropping. Towards the stall side the difference in the stage efficiency predicted can be larger than 2%. This will be further discussed in the next part. It is also observed that the unsteady simulation can cover a larger range towards the stall side while the steady simulation fails much earlier.

To further investigate the unsteady flow field, the instantaneous Mach number contour plot around 89.8% normalized mass flow is shown in Figure 5. Unlike the steady simulation, the shockwave predicted by the unsteady simulation is not 'stationary'. It interacts with the upstream impeller blade passing wake and oscillates in the diffuser passage. Moreover, this shock oscillation causes a leading edge separation on the diffuser vane pressure side. The flow circumferential uniformity is broken down and it is not periodic as a result. At instant 1 (Figure 5, left) the top vane in the view has a separation, while at instant 2 (Figure 5, right) the separation 'rotates' to the adjacent vane. It can also be observed that the Mach number magnitude is not the same in each passage. There are three passages where the Mach number is higher and its adjacent

passage has relatively lower Mach number. The shock strength in each passage is changing over time as the separation pattern rotates in the annulus.

Figure 5: Instantaneous contour plot of the Mach number at 50% span (for 89.8% normalized mass flow), left: instant 1; right: instant 2

This mechanism can never be captured by the steady simulations which will predict a stationary shockwave. The **loss generated from flow unsteadiness** is not included in the steady state performance prediction. In this case the unsteadiness is strong in the transonic flow which causes the big difference seen in Figure 3. Both the impeller and stage performance is overestimated by the steady simulation.

It should also be noticed that the shock wave goes across the ‘**mixing plane**’ in the steady simulation (as shown in Figure 4). As Denton mentioned in [9], the unsteady interaction between blade rows is strongest when the flow is transonic with shock waves and the mixing plane model becomes even more dubious in such cases. The mixing loss generated from the ‘mixing plane’ may not be similar to the loss generated from the unsteady transonic flow in between the two rows.

Furthermore, a frequency analysis has been carried out on the unsteady pressure signal measured by ‘numerical probes’ placed in the domain. The probes are at the exit of the IGV passage and the exit of the impeller passage (as shown in Figure 5 right). The probe in IGV domain is in the stationary frame of reference. The probe in impeller domain is in the rotating frame of reference, so it is rotating at the same speed as the impeller. Table 1 summarizes the main blade passing frequencies (BPF) within the domain.

RPM	12420		
Rotor Frequency [Hz]	207		
	Injector	Impeller	Diffuser
Blade number	7	11	7
BPF [Hz]	1449	2277	1449

Table 1 Main blade passing frequencies in the domain (100% speed)

The frequency spectrum captured by the probes signal is shown in Figure 6. The pressure disturbance is calculated by subtracting the time-mean value from the instantaneous value. Then the time series data is

transformed to frequency domain by FFT. At the IGV outlet (Figure 6 a) the numerical probe picks up the downstream impeller blade passing frequency (2277 Hz) and its 2nd order harmonic (In this case the impeller has a main blade and a splitter blade. The 22 blades also generate the 4554 Hz). At the impeller outlet (Figure 6 b) the frequency spectrum is more complex. First, the diffuser blade passing frequency (1449 Hz) is captured accurately and the signal is strongest among all frequency peaks. The 2nd order diffuser BPF is also visible but a lot weaker. Then the second strongest signal is at a relatively ‘low frequency’. This is due to the above described circumferential flow non-uniformity. The shock oscillation triggered separating flow in the diffuser is not steady and the pattern travels around the annulus, which generates another frequency signal apart from the BPF and its higher harmonics. The cross-coupling frequencies between the strong signals are also visible on the Spectrum.

Figure 6 Frequency Spectrum from unsteady pressure disturbance signal at around 50% span (for 89.8% normalized mass flow)

In addition, the magnitude difference between Figure 6 a) and b) suggests that the impeller/diffuser unsteady interaction is a lot stronger than the IGV/impeller blade row interaction. The frequency analysis also shows that the disturbance due to the flow non-uniformity is quite strong (of similar magnitude as the diffuser BPF). This again indicates that the influence of the transonic flow unsteadiness should be properly considered when predicting the performance. It is also important to the structural aspect of the machine, since it generates an additional low frequency pressure fluctuation that may excite the natural frequency of the machine.

Subsonic Flow:

In this part the 75% speed compressor performance and the flow field physics are discussed. Flow becomes

Figure 7 Total-to-total performances from both steady and unsteady simulations (75% speed)

subsonic at this rotational speed. Again the blade row interaction between the impeller and diffuser is studied in detail. The results from the whole annulus unsteady simulation are compared to these from single passage steady simulation. A comparison is also made to the transonic cases discussed above.

Figure 7 shows the total-to-total pressure ratio and the total-to-total polytropic efficiency of the impeller and the stage (impeller + diffuser). The mass flow rate and the pressure ratio are lower than the value in Figure 3 due to the reduced rotational speed. When comparing the results from unsteady simulations (red lines) to the ones from steady simulations (blue lines) it can be seen that the impeller performance predicted by the two agree well with each other. For the stage performance, the steady simulation predicts a higher pressure ratio and efficiency, but the difference is much smaller than in the transonic case (Figure 3). The maximum difference in efficiency is 1% while in the transonic case a difference over 2% can be observed. In addition, the overall trend predicted by the steady simulation is consistent with the unsteady

simulation. It should be pointed out that towards the choke side unsteady simulations were not carried out at higher mass flow rates. (It does not mean they failed to converge at such conditions.)

This indicates that when the unsteady interaction between impeller and diffuser blade rows is modeled by steady simulations with the mixing plane assumption, the loss generation is underestimated. The unsteadiness is not as strong as in the transonic case where a shockwave is oscillating across the blade row interface. Therefore, the steady simulation with the mixing plane model gives a better agreement with the unsteady simulation in this case.

It is also observed from the unsteady prediction (red lines) that towards the stall side when the static back pressure is further increased, the pressure ratio and efficiency go through a sudden drop and the mass flow rate is significantly reduced. Both the impeller and stage speed line show this trend. This will be further discussed when examining the unsteady flow field.

Similar to the analysis done for the transonic case, the flow field from steady simulation is examined first. Figure 8 shows the Mach number contour plot for the last stable points towards both the stall and the choke sides. At high speed conditions, the Mach number exiting the impeller passage is below 1.0 and there is no shockwave crossing the impeller/diffuser interface. Towards the choke side (Figure 8, right) there is a pressure side flow separation in the diffuser passage at both 10% span and 90% span positions. This flow separation is due to the incidence and triggers numerical oscillation, similar to the transonic case (Figure 4, right). On the other end of the speed line, when the flow rate is reduced towards the stall point, there is no visible separation on the suction side of the diffuser vane. This is different from the transonic case (Figure 4, left), where the shockwave induced a suction surface separation in the hub region.

Figure 8 Mach number contour plots from steady simulations (75% speed)

Next, the unsteady flow field at 75% rotational speed is studied. Figure 9 shows the instantaneous Mach number contour. The left view is for the condition near the peak efficiency point (45.8% normalized mass flow); the right view is for the last point towards stall side in Figure 7. Unlike the plot shown in Figure 5, there is no shockwave in the diffuser passages. At both conditions there is no severe separated flow in the diffuser domain and the diffuser flow is periodic along the annulus. The circumferential non-uniformity due to the shockwave/separation flow in the transonic case is not seen at this speed.

Figure 9: Instantaneous contour plot of the Mach number at 50% span for 75% speed, left: near peak efficiency; right: pre-stall

Furthermore, the instantaneous contour plot for the turbulence kinetic energy (TKE) has been examined. Figure 10 shows the TKE distribution at 90% span position. The left view is near peak efficiency point and the right view is towards stall condition. It can be observed that at the pre-stall condition, the flow is most turbulent at the impeller leading edge region. This is not the case for the transonic simulation, in which the region around the shock wave and the diffuser vane separation is most turbulent.

Figure 10: Instantaneous contour plot of turbulence kinetic energy at 90% span, left: near peak efficiency; right: pre-stall.

To further examine the flow near the impeller leading edge, a cross-section view is generated. Figure 11 shows the instantaneous contour plot of the axial velocity at the leading edge plane. The view looks into the impeller passage from the upstream direction. It can be seen that near the peak efficiency point (Figure 11, left) the axial velocity distribution shows good periodicity (11 impeller passages). The small differences in several passages are due to the beat mode (11 impeller passages and 7 IGV passages also results in a nodal diameter of 4). There is no

reverse flow observed under this condition. On the other hand at the pre-stall condition (Figure 11, right) there is significant reverse flow near the shroud which contributes to the ‘turbulent’ region seen in Figure 10 (right). It also causes the drop of pressure ratio and efficiency shown on the speed line (Figure 7).

Figure 11: Instantaneous contour plot of axial velocity at leading edge plane, left: near peak efficiency point; right: pre-stall condition

Again, a frequency analysis has been carried out on the unsteady pressure signal measured by ‘numerical probes’ placed in the domain (as shown in Figure 5 right). When the rotating speed is reduced to 75% the main blade passing frequencies within the domain are also lower due to the reduction of rotational speed. Table 2 summarizes the main BPFs for 75% speed.

RPM	9315		
Rotor Frequency [Hz]	155.25		
	Injector	Impeller	Diffuser
Blade number	7	11	7
BPF [Hz]	1086.75	1707.75	1086.75

Table 2 Main blade passing frequencies in the domain (75% speed).

The frequency spectrum captured by the probe signal is shown in Figure 12. Again, at the IGV outlet (Figure 12 a) the numerical probe picks up the downstream impeller blade passing frequency (1707.75 Hz) and its 2nd order harmonic (or impeller ‘main blade + splitter’ frequency) 3415.5 Hz. There is also a lower frequency peak which could be due to the disturbance from the impeller revolution. Also, the magnitude of the IGV probe signal is very weak (lower than 6×10^{-3} psi) at the near peak efficiency point. The fluctuation only grows much stronger towards stall side when the inducer flow separates near the shroud, as shown in Figure 10.

At the impeller outlet (Figure 12 b) the diffuser blade passing frequency is captured accurately and the higher order diffuser BPFs are also visible but a lot weaker. Unlike the frequency spectrum for the transonic flow (Figure 6 b), there are no additional frequency peaks from the probe signal. This is because the shock oscillation and the rotating disturbance from separated flow do not exist in this subsonic flow field. It is also noticed that the

magnitude of the pressure disturbance in this case is a lot smaller than the transonic scenario. The strongest peak is below 0.3 psi while in Figure 6 b the strongest peaks are over 0.5 psi. This suggests that the unsteady blade row interaction is much stronger and more complex when the flow is transonic.

Figure 12 Frequency Spectrum from unsteady pressure signal at around 50% span (75% speed, near peak efficiency point)

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In summary, numerical simulations have been carried out for a centrifugal compressor with a vane diffuser. Both unsteady and steady calculations are conducted. The performance predictions from the two are compared to each other and the differences are discussed. The results show that from high rotational speed to low rotational speed the stage flow changes from transonic to subsonic. The unsteady blade row interaction is very different for the two scenarios.

For transonic stage flow the shockwave oscillation triggers the diffuser passage flow separation. The flow pattern is circumferentially non-uniform and the disturbance travels along the annulus. Frequency analysis has been carried out to identify this pressure fluctuation. For subsonic stage flow the major blade row interaction is from the blade passing wake. There is no circumferential non-uniformity in the diffuser flow.

As to the numerical accuracy, the steady simulation with mixing plane assumption tends to over predict the pressure ratio and efficiency for the configuration studied. This is because the loss generation due to the flow unsteadiness is not accurately modelled. As described previously in [10] [11] the unsteady wakes will affect the boundary layer flow and the secondary flow in the

passage, and therefore affect the loss generated. Previous work [12] has also shown that compared to test data the steady state simulations over predicted the pressure ratio and efficiency in a centrifugal compressor stage; while the unsteady simulations predict an efficiency that agrees better with the test data. The issue becomes more serious in the transonic case where the shockwave oscillates and its influence on both the upstream and the downstream flow is very strong. Both the impeller and stage performance are over predicted by the steady simulation. In the subsonic case, the impeller performance agrees well with the unsteady simulation, but the stage performance is over estimated.

It is important to identify and quantify this difference because in most design practices the steady simulations are still the default choice due to faster iteration time and fewer requirements on the computational resources. However, to evaluate the performance at various rotational speeds for a machine which can function at different flow conditions, some attention should be paid to the transonic flow simulation. When generating the performance map for the high speed conditions, the flow unsteadiness should be carefully considered.

In addition, the flow field towards stability limit was examined. Towards the choke side the diffuser vane flow separation due to the flow incidence is the main trigger of instability. Towards the stall side the mechanism is more complex. For transonic stage flow the shockwave-induced flow separation on the diffuser suction side at hub region becomes unstable, while for the subsonic case an inducer shroud separation happens before the diffuser flow shows any separation. Whether this separation will trigger instability (if the flow rate is further reduced) needs more study. The future work should try to capture the onset of the rotating instability and identify some critical flow parameters, such as velocity angle and its variation, which will help to better understand the off-design flow physics and the machine performance at such conditions. This knowledge can also help in both the design and system control phases.

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